

Dendrochronological analysis of wood components of the Antwerp altarpiece at Ringsaker Church, Norway.

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Fig. 1. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. The characteristic Antwerp brand can be seen on many of the sculptures on the work. (photo Aoife Daly).

Introduction

In this study, a range of selected wood components from the Antwerp (fig. 1) altarpiece at Ringsaker Church, Moelv, Norway, have been analysed dendrochronologically, to determine the date and region of origin of the oak trees that were used to make them. The selection of the components to be analysed was highly dependent on how readily the parts could be removed from the caisson of the work or on how readily the tree-rings, in places, were discernible to allow reliable non-invasive measurement. A total of 17 objects have been analysed in this way.

Non-invasive dendrochronological analysis has proved successful in recent years, both through CT-scanning of oak objects and through analysis of exposed tree-rings on objects, when possible (Bill et al 2012, Daly & Streeton 2017). For the analysis of the altarpiece at Ringsaker Church, tree-rings were clear on ten wood elements so, apart from cleaning to remove dust, no invasive techniques were used for the tree-ring measurement of these. The remaining seven objects were gently pared on the base, with a razor blade, prior to analysis. This report outlines the results of the analysis.

Fig. 2. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. The Last Judgement scene. The sculpture components that were analysed dendrochronologically are labelled D4 to D9. (photo Tone Olstad, illustration Aoife Daly).

Macro photographs, with a ruler for scale, were taken along all the selected wood components. Measuring was carried out from these images using the program Able Image Analyser, and for the analysis and the calculation of the t -value (" t -test"), the programs "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. An extensive network of master and site chronologies for Northern Europe were consulted to find the dating for the tree-ring series. To estimate the felling dates of the oak trees that were used for the boards and sculptures a sapwood average for Northern Poland (15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)) is utilised.

The Last Judgement

The Last Judgement composition (fig. 2), on the plinth of the altarpiece, is constructed using a number of sculpted oak blocks. As these had been removed during previous conservation work, it was possible to remove these pieces again to gain access to the wood components. Six components are analysed from this composition. Five are analysed invasively, as the tree-rings in the base cross-sections were not clear enough without paring.

The correlation between the tree-ring curves from the sculptures from the Last Judgement suggest two clear groupings, representing just two trees (see also table 1).

Fig. 3. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. The base of the sculpture of the lion from the Last Judgement scene (D5). The tree-rings of the main wood block are pared (along a narrow band just above the ruler) to enable reliable measurement (photo Aoife Daly).

Fig. 4. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. The Christ sculpture from the Last Judgement scene (D8) (photo Aoife Daly).

Tree 1 (highlighted with green in fig. 8 and table 1)

Two sculptures belong to tree 1. The lion(?) at the right of the composition is numbered D5. The sculpture is made from two main oak blocks with smaller additional pieces added (fig. 3). The largest rear block is analysed. It contains 265 tree-rings, all heartwood.

Fig. 5. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. View of the base of the Christ sculpture from the Last Judgement scene (D8), prior to paring for dendrochronological analysis (photo Aoife Daly).

Fig. 6. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. The sculpture of four figures from the Last Judgement scene (D4). (photo Aoife Daly).

The central Christ sculpture (D8) also belongs to tree 1. This consists of a finely carved figure standing on a roughly carved oak block, all made from a single board or block (fig. 4). The block was pared on the base (fig. 5 shows the base before paring) for dendrochronological analysis. The block contains 262 tree-rings, all heartwood.

The correlation (Student 1908) between the tree-ring curves from these two sculptures displays highly significant similarity achieving a t -value of $t = 16.37$ at their cross-matching position. Visual comparison of the tree-rings curves also strongly suggests that the two blocks are derived from a single tree. Tree 1 is dated. The outermost measured tree-ring is on sculpture D5, and this ring was formed in AD 1504. No remains of sapwood have been observed. Allowing for missing sapwood we can estimate that tree 1 was felled after AD 1514 (see fig. 8).

Fig. 7. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. Macro view of the base of the sculpture of three figures and the devil from the Last Judgement scene (D7). The outermost tree-rings are on the left edge, where three sapwood rings are identified (photo Aoife Daly).

Tree 2

A sculpture of four figures is given the number D4 (fig 6). It is sculpted from a single oak block or board and contains 229 tree-rings, only heartwood.

The sculpture of the gates to heaven (D6) at the left of the composition (fig. 2) contains 207 tree-rings, only heartwood.

One sculpture, of three figures and the devil (D7), has sapwood preserved (fig. 7). Finally, a fourth sculpture, of five figures (D9), contains 238 tree-rings, again only heartwood. These four sculptures have highly similar tree-ring curves (highlighted with blue in table 1) that all four can have been made from the same tree, which we will call tree 2. Tree 2 is dated. Allowing for missing sapwood we can estimate that tree 2 was felled in c. AD 1521-35 (see fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. The diagram illustrates the chronological position of the dated wood elements. The shading of the bars corresponds to the highlighting in tables 1 and 2. The purple vertical line marks the years 1527 to 1547 when Ansten Jonsson Skonk was priest at the church. The dating of the oak components falls neatly within this timeframe. (illustration Aoife Daly).

	Z268013a D13	Z268005a D5	Z268008a D8	Z268004a D4	Z268007a D7	Z268006a D6	Z268009aa D9	Z268012a D12	Z268014a D14	Z2680109 D10	Z268015b D15	Z268016a D16	Z268011a D11	Z268017a D17	Z268001a D1
Average Z268M002	*	3.47	4.63	3.61	3.62	2.04	0.45	0.53	1.37	0.77	1.91	\	\	-	-
Same tree 1	3.47	*	16.37	5.71	5.15	5.77	4.72	0.87	2.12	1.22	2.41	0.74	0.83	1.11	1.80
	4.63	16.37	*	5.26	5.2	4.77	3.79	1.10	1.97	2.08	3.22	1.63	1.80	0.9	1.52
Same tree 2	3.61	5.71	5.26	*	17.11	17.0	10.67	4.08	3.26	3.17	3.00	1.63	2.50	1.73	2.12
	3.62	5.15	5.2	17.11	*	16.11	10.47	5.26	2.39	3.94	1.67	0.6	1.64	0.75	3.10
	2.04	5.77	4.77	17.0	16.11	*	12.47	5.66	2.51	3.33	1.18	0.25	1.35	0.42	2.92
	0.45	4.72	3.79	10.67	10.47	12.47	*	4.44	2.49	2.31	0.70	0.14	1.17	0.95	2.70
	0.53	0.87	1.10	4.08	5.26	5.66	4.44	*	2.17	3.29	0.53	0.88	1.00	0.63	2.24
	1.37	2.12	1.97	3.26	2.39	2.51	2.49	2.17	*	3.17	2.72	1.55	1.83	0.70	1.93
	0.77	1.22	2.08	3.17	3.94	3.33	2.31	3.29	3.17	*	2.69	2.16	2.70	1.97	2.50
Same tree 3	1.91	2.41	3.22	3.00	1.67	1.18	0.70	0.53	2.72	2.69	*	11.17	8.83	3.1	2.17
	\	0.74	1.63	1.63	0.6	0.25	0.14	0.88	1.55	2.16	11.17	*	15.48	4.06	2.88
	\	0.83	1.80	2.5	1.64	1.35	1.17	1.00	1.83	2.7	8.83	15.48	*	1.81	2.67
	-	1.11	0.9	1.73	0.75	0.42	0.95	0.63	0.70	1.97	3.10	4.06	1.81	*	2.90
	-	1.80	1.52	2.12	3.10	2.92	2.70	2.24	1.93	2.50	2.17	2.88	2.67	2.90	*

Table 1. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. Result of the correlation (*t*-value) between the tree-ring curves from each board with each other.

The caisson structure

Seven wood elements from the caisson were analysed (see fig. 9). These were chosen on the basis of the accessibility of the timber cross section. The tops of two vertically-placed side planks (D13 and D14) of the main caisson were pared for analysis (fig. 10), while five timber components forming the curved tops of the two doors were analysed non-invasively (fig. 11).

Fig. 9. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. The altarpiece. The wood components that were analysed dendrochronologically are labelled D10 to D16. (photo and illustration Aoife Daly).

The two caisson sides

The top of side D14 was cut at a knot in the wood so the cross-section here had many distorted rings, which were not measured. The 50 outermost tree-rings were prepared and measured however. The full cross-section of D13 could be accessed however, and this contains 180 tree-rings (fig. 10). These two side planks, both of which only have heartwood preserved, are dated. Allowing for missing sapwood the tree for D13 was felled after AD 1461 and the tree for D14 was felled after AD 1478.

The curved door tops comprise of several sculpted wood components. D10 from the left door contains 138 tree-rings, all heartwood, and is dated. It is from a tree felled after AD 1500.

D12 is also from the left door and it contains 99 tree-rings again all heartwood. This piece is from a tree felled after AD 1508.

Tree 3

The curved components D11 from the left door and D15 and D16, both from the right-hand door, are so similar in their tree-ring curves, these might be made from the same tree, and we call this tree 3 (this group is highlighted with orange in table 1). None of these have sapwood preserved. Tree 3 was felled after c. AD 1518 (fig. 8).

Fig. 10. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. The side plank D13 was pared for analysis. (photo Aoife Daly).

Fig. 11. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. The curved upper parts of the doors were sculpted from several oak blocks. The tree-rings were sufficiently visible on several of these allowing non-invasive analysis (photo Aoife Daly).

Eucharistic Man of Sorrows

Central in the altarpiece is a gated panel containing the Eucharistic Man of Sorrows. Three wood components from this composition were analysed, two parts from the sculpture and one small board from the scene.

The sculpture of the bleeding Christ stands on a small oak plinth (D1) (fig. 12). The underside of the plinth was very clean, and the tree-rings were clear, so this was analysed non-invasively. The plinth contains 159 tree-rings, including 4

sapwood rings. The tree that this plinth was made from was felled c. AD 1525-39 (fig. 8).

On the back of the sculpted body of the Eucharistic Man of Sorrows (D2) the tree-rings were also clearly visible, and these were measured non-invasively. A total of 158 tree-rings were observed (all heartwood), but the first 30 were less clear, so these are excluded from the final tree-ring curve. In spite of a series of 132 rings this wooden element could not be dated.

A little thin oak panel, D17, is part of the background scenery in this composition. This was measured non-invasively on the longitudinal section at the back of this piece. It contains 157 tree-rings, all heartwood, and is dated. The tree for this panel was felled after AD 1519 (fig. 8).

Fig. 12. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. The Eucharistic Man of Sorrows (D2) stands on a separate oak plinth (D1). The tree-rings were sufficiently visible on the back of the figure (D2) and on the base of the little plinth (D1) to allow non-invasive analysis. (photo Aoife Daly).

The nativity scene

Just one sculpted part, D3, of the nativity scene could be taken out of the composition to be examined. It contains less than 50 rings and even though the rings were not sufficiently clear for analysis, non-invasive measurement of the base of this was nevertheless attempted. A series of 42 rings was attained but this could not be dated.

Filenames	-	-	Average Z268M002	
-	start	dates	AD 1215	
-	dates	end	AD 1515	
Z2261M01 ne...	AD 1098	AD 1522	13.84	Køge ship planks 18 timbers (Daly 2019a)
Z2261M03 do...	AD 1264	AD 1537	13.25	Køge ship double planks 7 timbers (Daly 2019b)
BALTIC1	AD 1156	AD 1597	12.80	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
00751M01	AD 1113	AD 1463	9.45	Vejdyb ship 14 trees (Daly 1997)
H11EOM01	AD 1260	AD 1495	8.65	Bordesholmer Altar 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
Z084M002	AD 1152	AD 1438	8.44	Skaftö wreck barrel 11 timbers (Daly 2013a)
KL15sALC1 short	AD 1366	AD 1536	8.25	Klaipeda Castle 11 timbers (Puckiene pers comm)
stirlingdoorsM1	AD 1270	AD 1524	8.20	Stirling Castle doors 10 timbers (Crone pers comm)
Z256M001	AD 1239	AD 1479	8.06	Missale Nidrosiense CT 5 timbers (Daly 2019b)
Z103M tracery	AD 1348	AD 1495	7.99	Slagen altertavle Norge tracery 4 timbers (Daly 2013b)
Z163M001	AD 1200	AD 1422	7.97	St Anne sculpture C2912 2 timbers (Daly 2016)
B019M002	AD 1374	AD 1574	7.82	Helsingør Kulturværft two barrels 5 timbers (Daly 2009)
StJM1	AD 1284	AD 1490	7.35	St Jakobs Church Riga 3 timbers (Daly & Zunde 2017)
H019M001 barrel	AD 1355	AD 1545	7.17	Aalborg Algade 16 barrel 5 timbers (Daly 2018)
Z131005a	AD 1285	AD 1442	7.14	Bygland altarpiece side plank 5 bottom (Daly 2015)
Z054m001	AD 1235	AD 1448	7.14	Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 planks 5 timbers (Daly 2010)
PERTHM6	AD 1225	AD 1499	7.13	Perth Museum panels Baltic (Crone pers comm)
vilniusZP	AD 1104	AD 1530	6.79	Vilnius 29 timbers (Puckiene pers comm)
Z112M004	AD 1287	AD 1513	6.60	Veien altarpiece Oslo 3 timbers (Daly 2014b)
vilnioak	AD 1202	AD 1530	6.58	Vilnius Castle oak 20 timbers (Puckiene pers comm revised Daly unpubl)
OeqannM1	AD 1243	AD 1479	6.37	Saint Anne retable Niguliste 2 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z101M001	AD 1317	AD 1493	6.19	Kvæfjord 1 altertavle Norge corpus back planks same tree 4 timbers (Daly 2014c)
Memel Klaipeda	AD 1288	AD 1580	6.19	Memel Klaipeda (Brazauskas 2006)
B0352M02	AD 1386	AD 1489	6.13	Roskilde Stændertorvet tøndestaver 3 timbers (Daly 2015)
Z114&5 T1	AD 1348	AD 1542	6.04	Cranach-Vejle Luther Melancthon P1 & P3 (Daly 2014d)
B3n_T19	AD 1307	AD 1631	5.99	Baltic 3 new 19 trees (Tyers pers comm)
se613m01	AD 1197	AD 1464	5.96	Hull Blaydes Staithe 3 timbers (Sheffield Uni revised Daly 2007)
Z152002a	AD 1318	AD 1490	5.88	Holmedal epitaph Bergen plank 2 (Daly unpubl)
Z117001a	AD 1226	AD 1470	5.76	Sittow Portrait of Christian 2 base end KMSsp789 (Daly 2014e)
cesis_c4	AD 1398	AD 1536	5.64	Cesis Castle Cesu pilseta Latvia (Zunde pers comm)
P802001m	AD 1209	AD 1401	5.42	Poland Krupy (Wazny pers comm)
0207M002	AD 1200	AD 1402	5.39	Dokøen vrag 3 3 timbers Bonde & Eriksen 2002)
1HA00M01	AD 1450	AD 1590	5.37	Haarlem Wilsonplein barrel 3 timbers (van Dalen pers comm)
B0261M01	AD 1380	AD 1493	5.28	Køge forundersøgelses barrel B1 2 timbers (Daly 2013c)
H025M002 pl	AD 1155	AD 1596	5.26	Vingårdsgade Ålborg pl 5 timbers (Daly & Daly 2019)
KlaipedaKL	AD 1266	AD 1536	5.11	Klaipeda 17 timbers (Puckiene pers comm)
Z151M001	AD 1310	AD 1499	5.10	Lauenburg epitaph Schleswig 2 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Oeqmar1a	AD 1270	AD 1454	5.05	Maria retable Niguliste corpus plank 5 (Daly unpubl)

Table 2. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. Result of the correlation between the average curve Z268M002 and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z268014a D14	
-	start	dates	AD 1419	
-	dates	end	AD 1468	
Z181201a	AD 1416	AD 1578	5.45	Kirkestræde 6 A37 Tøndel latrine (Daly & Nielsen 2016)
Z103M4&7&8 ...	AD 1351	AD 1495	4.53	Slagen tracery 3 timbers (Daly 2013b)
BALTIC1	AD 1156	AD 1597	4.05	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)

Table 3. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve Z268014a from sculpture D4 and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Provenance

The tree-ring curves from the dated wood components from the Ringsaker altarpiece cross-match with each other as shown in table 1. The three strongly correlating groups, representing three trees, are highlighted in green (tree 1), blue (tree 2) and orange (tree 3). Trees 1 and 2, along with D13 and D12 form a group and are averaged to a mean curve, Z268M002 (highlighted with turquoise), representing four trees and of 301 years length. The remaining dated components; tree 3, D14, D10, D17 and D1, do not form a group within this material. These are dating independently.

In tables 2 to 7 the correlation between these dated components and a wide range of Northern European oak tree-ring datasets are shown. The material is dating strongly with Southern and Eastern Baltic oak tree-ring datasets.

As many of the Baltic tree-ring chronologies are built from oak that was exported to Western Europe, it has not as yet been possible to say where, precisely, that these trees grew in the extensive Southern Baltic region. In the extensive corpus of dendrochronologically analysed oak, used as supports for fine art and for ecclesiastical sculpture in the c. 15th to 17th centuries, it is possible to distinguish between different groups of the Southern Baltic timber, (named Baltic 1, Baltic 2 and Baltic 3 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)) and these groups most probably represent forests in different areas within the region.

The material analysed from Ringsaker demonstrates on the one hand how a single composition as represented in the analysis of the six parts from Judgement Day is composed of a very closely related wood supply, whereas components from elsewhere in the work represent a wider timber supply to Antwerp from the Baltics. The altarpiece is made from oak from both the Baltic 1 source (the Judgement Day group etc (tables 2, 3 and 7) and the Baltic 2 source (tables 4, 5 and 6). Recent research into the source of these so-called Baltic groups suggest that the Baltic 1 group is from eastwards in the region, while Baltic 2 might have had a source closer towards the Vistula.

Filenames	-	-	Z2680109 D10	
-	start	dates	AD 1353	
-	dates	end	AD 1490	
BALTIC2	AD 1257	AD 1615	7.24	Baltic 2 40 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
se617M01	AD 1100	AD 1396	5.91	New Baxtergate Grims 5 timbers (Sheffield Uni revised Daly 2007)
02071M01	AD 1126	AD 1414	5.88	Dokøen Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001)
os160_t7	AD 1138	AD 1382	5.67	York Vicars Choral Large Table 7 boards (Tyers pers comm)
Z105M002	AD 1297	AD 1479	5.60	Berg tabernacle Norway 1&4 2 timbers (Daly 2014a)
BALTIC1	AD 1156	AD 1597	5.29	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
00751M03	AD 1221	AD 1456	5.07	Vejdyb ship 4 trees (Daly 1997)
0628002M	AD 1225	AD 1445	4.98	Torun Joh Church (Wazny pers comm)
Z2261M01 ne...	AD 1098	AD 1522	4.95	Køge ship planks 18 timbers (Daly 2019a)
Z2261M03 do...	AD 1264	AD 1537	4.12	Køge ship double planks 7 timbers (Daly 2019a)

Table 4. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve Z2680109 from the curved left-hand door D10 and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z268011& 15&16 st D11 D15 D16	
-	start	dates	AD 1411	
-	dates	end	AD 1508	
BALTIC2	AD 1257	AD 1615	7.71	Baltic 2 40 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
HEADSx3	AD 1372	AD 1513	5.20	Stirling heads Baltic (Crone pers comm)
B3_NPG	AD 1318	AD 1624	4.47	Baltic 3 new 15 timbers (Tyers pers comm)
BALTIC1	AD 1156	AD 1597	4.20	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)

Table 5. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve for tree 3 from the elements forming the curved doors D11, D15 & D16 and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z268017a D17	
-	start	dates	AD1353	
-	dates	end	AD1509	
BALTIC2	AD1257	AD1615	7.77	Baltic 2 40 timbers [Hillam & Tyers 1995]
G311YZ02	AD1324	AD1575	5.84	Hann.Münden 35 timbers [Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007]
Z060003a	AD1398	AD1552	5.17	Pieter Bruegel elder Christ money lenders upper plank (Daly 2011)
DM200003	AD1004	AD1970	4.71	Weserbergland [Göttingen Uni]
DM200004	30BC	AD1960	4.67	G Weser [Göttingen Uni]
G312AZ01	AD1354	AD1468	4.59	Göttingen 13 timbers [Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007]
0628003M	AD1351	AD1467	4.27	Torun Jacob (Wazny pers comm)
0952910S	AD1343	AD1569	4.24	St.Katharinen (Wazny pers comm)

Table 6. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve Z268017a from the small panel D17 and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Filenames	-	-	Z268001a D1	
-	start	dates	AD 1362	
-	dates	end	AD 1520	
BALTIC1	AD 1156	AD 1597	6.02	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
BAL3_IT_AD ...	AD 1307	AD 1633	5.67	Baltic 3 67 timbers (Tyers & Daly unpubl)
0EQKTVM001	AD 1295	AD 1549	5.60	Tallinn Christ Money-lenders Temple 3 timbers (Daly & Läänelaid 2011)
Z2261M01 ne...	AD 1098	AD 1522	5.53	Køge ship planks 18 timbers (Daly 2019a)
B3n_T19	AD 1307	AD 1631	5.36	Baltic 3 new 19 trees (Tyers pers comm)
00751M01	AD 1113	AD 1463	5.24	Vejdyb ship 14 trees (Daly 1997)

Table 7. Ringsaker Church altarpiece, Moelv, Norway. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring curve Z268001a from sculpture D1 and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Discussion

In fig. 8 a purple vertical line marks the years from AD 1527 to 1547, the two decades when Ansten Jonsson Skonk was priest at the church. It was he who commissioned the altarpiece from Robert Moreau in Antwerp (online resource 1). The dating of the oak components in this analysis fall very neatly into this historical timeline.

In terms of the wood used for the piece the provenance determination shows that this altarpiece built in Antwerp is another example of the shipment of the hugely sought-after so-called Baltic oak, popular over many centuries as an essential artists' material.

It is a period where we see extensive trade of Baltic timber to western Europe, especially of long, straight boards and planks of knot-free oak. As the tables of correlation show, this material was used extensively for ecclesiastical and secular sculpture and art, for ship planking and even for barrel-making.

Online resources

1. https://www.nordenskirker.dk/Tidligere/Ringsaker_kirke/Ringsaker_kirke.htm accessed 23.12.2019.

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Average ring width (mm.)	Interpretation / felling
Boards											
Z268001a	Ringsaker Church Smertens Mannen base plinth D1 non-invasive QUSP	159	AD1362	AD1520	G	4	N	R	S1	1.11	AD1525-39
Z2680029	Ringsaker Church Smertens Mannen body D2 non-invasive QUSP	132			G	0	N	?	H1	1.05	undated
Z268003a	Ringsaker Church 2 nativity figures D3 non-invasive QUSP	42			G	0	N	R	H1	1.63	undated
Z268004a	Ringsaker Church Judgement 4 figures D4 QUSP	229	AD1283	AD1511	G	0	N	R	H1	1.11	AD1521-35
Z268005a	Ringsaker Church Judgement Lion relief D5 QUSP	265	AD1240	AD1504	G	0	N	R	H1	0.83	after AD1514
Z268006a	Ringsaker Church Judgement church relief D6 QUSP	207	AD1306	AD1512	G	0	N	R	H1	1.11	AD1521-35
Z268007a	Ringsaker Church Judgement 3 figures + devil D7 QUSP	210	AD1306	AD1515	G	3	N	R	S1	1.04	AD1521-35
Z268008a	Ringsaker Church Judgement central Christ figure D8 QUSP	262	AD1215	AD1476	G	0	N	R	H1	0.94	after AD1514
Z268009aa	Ringsaker Church Judgement 5 figures D9 non-invasive QUSP	238	AD1272	AD1509	G	0	N	R	H1	1.18	AD1521-35
Z2680109	Ringsaker Church caisse curved door top D10 non-invasive QUSP	138	AD1353	AD1490	G	0	N	?	H1	1.06	after AD1500
Z268011a	Ringsaker Church caisse curved door top D11 non-invasive QUSP	73	AD1436	AD1508	G	0	N	O	H1	1.78	after AD1518
Z268012a	Ringsaker Church caisse curved door top D12 non-invasive QUSP	99	AD1400	AD1498	G	0	N	O	H1	1.41	after AD1508
Z268013a	Ringsaker Church main caisse wainscot D13 QUSP	180	AD1272	AD1451	G	0	N	R	H1	1.07	after AD1461
Z268014a	Ringsaker Church main caisse wainscot D14 QUSP	50	AD1419	AD1468	G	0	N	R	H1	0.69	after AD1478
Z268015b	Ringsaker Church right door curved caisse D15 non-invasive QUSP	95	AD1411	AD1505	G	0	N	?	H1	1.47	after AD1518
Z268016a	Ringsaker Church right door curved caisse D16 non-invasive QUSP	78	AD1431	AD1508	G	0	N	?	H1	1.72	after AD1518
Z268017a	Ringsaker Church small panel D17 non-invasive QUSP	157	AD1353	AD1509	G	0	N	?	H1	1.52	after AD1519
Same tree											
Z268004&6&7&9 st	Ringsaker Church Judgement 4 figures D4 D6 D7 D9 QUSP	244	AD1272	AD1515	?	0	U	?	N	1.11	AD1521-35
Z268005&8 st	Ringsaker Church Judgement same tree D5 D8 Christ and Lion QUSP	290	AD1215	AD1504	?	0	U	?	N	0.89	after AD1514
Z268011&15 &16 st	Ringsaker Church caisse same tree D11 D15 D16 QUSP	98	AD1411	AD1508	G	0	N	?	H1	1.57	after AD1518
Averages											
Z268M002	Ringsaker 4 timbers [Daly 2019] QUSP	301	AD1215	AD1515						1.09	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoiife Daly, Ph.D.											
15 December 2019											